

STUDY OF PSYCHONEUROSIS OF HEALTHCARE EMPLOYEES IN PUBLIC HOSPITAL AT RAIPUR*

BY

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ABSTRACT

An effectively working health care system is not possible without a satisfied workforce and workplace stress. Workplace stress not only impact the employee in an organization but it overall hinders the organization and its output. Psychoneurosis is one of the examples of stress-related disorders included in the national lists of occupational diseases. Psychoneurosis is not a disease it's a disorder (a neurosis based on emotional conflict) which can arise at any time during the service period of an employee and therefore its assessment and measures to control is of utmost importance so that organization can give productive outputs. The objective of the study is to analyze the level of psychoneurosis among the healthcare employees. The data was collected using General Healthcare Questionnaire (GHQ12)& analyzed using SPSS-9. The level of psychoneurosis measured in Four-Point Likert's scale rating. The result of the study showed that the age of the respondents, marital status is independent of psychoneurosis. Psychoneurosis are dependent on designation of the employees, working experience and presence of stress other than that related to job. Majority of the respondents shows high psychoneurosis and displayed both mental and physical symptoms. From the analysis the inference drawn is that respondents who are having high psychoneurosis are dissatisfied with their job.

KEYWORDS

Psychoneurosis, Public Hospital, Healthcare Employees, General Healthcare Questionnaires.

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Introduction

The psychoneurosis is minor mental disorder characterized by inner struggles and disturbed social relationship. Two essential features of psychoneurosis are that they are precipitated by emotional stresses, conflicts and frustrations and that they are most effectively treated by psychological techniques. They are not produced by physical disorders and do not respond to routine medical attention.

Symptoms of Psychoneurosis

The symptoms of psychoneurotic are such that compulsory hospitalization or segregation is unnecessary. A few patients voluntarily seek hospital treatment, but the majority lives at home and usually continue with their customary business and social activity.

Psychoneurotic symptoms are extremely varied. Some of the more frequent psychological complaints are anxiety, depressed spirits, inability to concentrate, or make decisions, memory disturbances, irritability, morbid doubts, obsessions, irrational fears, insomnia, compulsions and inability to enjoy social relations. Physical symptom which are generally essential bodily concomitants of strong emotions and conflicts, include loss of voluntary control over certain sensory functions, shortness of breath, persistent tension, fatigue, headaches, gastrointestinal disturbances and multiple aches and pains.

Incidence of Psychoneurosis

Approximately 5-10 % of the population exhibit psychoneurotic symptom at any given time. As many as 20% of the people have shown or will show psychoneurotic reactions at critical moments in their lives.

Etiology of Psychoneuroses:

1. Physical factors: Because of the close interdependence of mind and body it is incorrect to state that physical factors play no role in the development of psychoneurosis for e.g., physical exhaustion may so weaken the mental resources of the individual as to facilitate the appearance of neurotic symptoms. However, such instances are rare.
2. Constitution: Heredity and early environment and training are the main factors determining of constitutional make-up. When unfavorable they present the development of a well-integrated sturdy personality and thus facilitate the appearance of psychoneurotic reaction when the individual is confronted with some disturbing or intolerable situation.

Classification of Psychoneuroses

The four types of psychoneurosis most generally recognized are hysteria, neurasthenia, anxiety and psychasthenia.

Aim

The aim of the study is to find out the level of and possible causes of psychoneurosis.

Methodology

Study Design and Sample - A Cross sectional study using Non-Probabilistic Convenience sampling; and a stratified random sampling was conducted in public hospital in Raipur, Chhattisgarh which has more than 400 + beds. Data regarding number of staffs couldn't be found from the hospital but all those who were accessible from hospital including staff, part time employees, or ad hoc basis AV staff were involved in patient care were considered as study population. The sample involved health care worker of different strata including residential doctors, staff nurses, administration & management, paramedical staff & technicians, security. A well-structured questionnaire used for collecting the primary data from the employees which is used as the instrument for data. The 12-item General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12) was used for measuring mental disorders. The different parameters under each area selected for the study were asked to be rated by the respondents on a Four-Point Likert scale rating. Analysis carried out by assigning scores to these ratings given by the respondents to the different parameters under each area.

Data Collection and Analysis - A total of 300 questionnaire were distributed and collected over a period of two months. Out of 300, 232 responded (Response Rate of 78%) with the complete answers and all necessary precaution were taken to ensure that there are no missing values. The data was analyzed using (SPSS-9). Chi-Square Tests and correlation analysis was carried out.

Limitation - Limitation of this study are its use of self-reporting questionnaire, which rely on the honesty of those completing them and its cross-sectional design. It is not possible to assess completely the psychosomatic disorders within the given timeframe.

Result

A study sample had shown (69.4%) Males and (30.6%) Females and 47.0% of them were in 20-25 Year Age Group. Were 42.7% married and 57.3% unmarried. 35 Resident Doctors, 70 Nurse Staff, 35 Admin & Management, 60 Paramed & Others, 32 Security. 141 worked in the hospital for less than 1 year, 83 for 1-5 year, 3 for 5-10 years, 5 had been more than 10 years, were 174 are having below 10,000 salaries. And 58 were having more than 10,000 salaries.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of Health care Workers Working in Public Tertiary Care Hospital of Raipur Chhattisgarh.

Socio Demographic Variable		Frequency	Percent
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Gender	Male	161	69.4
	Female	71	30.6
Age	20-25	109	47.0
	25-30	64	27.6
	30-35	37	15.9
	Above 35	22	9.5
Marital Status	Unmarried	133	57.3
	Married	99	42.7
Designation of the respondent	Res Doc	35	15.1
	Nursing	70	30.2
	Admin & Management	35	15.1
	Paramed & Others	60	25.9
	Security	32	13.8
Working experience	Less than 1 year	141	60.8
	1-5 year	83	35.8
	5-10 year	3	1.3
	More than 10 years	5	2.2
Salary of the respondent	Below 10,000	174	75.0
	More than 10,000	58	25.0

Chi- Square Test for each socio demographic characteristic:

1. Chi-Square Tests for Age of the respondents and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of Age group

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of Age group

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.872(a)	6	.438

Interpretation: Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the age group and psychoneurosis are independent of each other i.e.; people of any age can have psychoneurosis.

2. Chi-Square Tests for marital status of the respondents and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of marital status of the respondents

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of marital status of the respondents

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.153(a)	2	.926

Interpretation: Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the marital status of the respondents and psychoneurosis are independent of each other i.e.; marital status of the respondent is not the determining factor for psychoneurosis.

3. Chi-Square Tests for working experience of the respondents and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of working experience of the respondents

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of working experience of the respondents

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.935(a)	6	.001

Interpretation: Since the p value is less than 0.1 therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the working experience of the respondents and psychoneurosis are dependent of each other i.e.; people who are having less working experience are showing high psychoneurosis.

4. Chi-Square Tests for presence of stress other than job and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of presence of stress other than job

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of presence of stress other than job

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.469(a)	2	.005

Interpretation: Since the p value is less than 0.1 therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the presence of stress other than job and psychoneurosis are dependent of each other i.e.; if the people are having stress factors (personal projects etc.) other than job than they are suffering from psychoneurosis.

Table 2. Frequency Table for psychoneurosis and its various dimensions.

Job Satisfaction Variables		Frequency	Percentage
	much less than before	8	3.4
Ability to concentrate	same as before	145	62.5
	more than before	63	27.2
	much more than before	16	6.9
Sleep Cycle	much less than before	51	22.0
	same as before	114	49.1
	more than before	59	25.4
	much more than before	8	3.4
Playing a useful part in hospital working process	much less than before	15	6.5
	same as before	150	64.6
	more than before	58	25.0
	much more than before	9	3.9
Make decisions related to their department	much less than before	15	6.5
	same as before	150	64.7
	more than before	60	25.9
	much more than before	7	3.0
Constantly under strain	much less than before	32	13.8
	same as before	130	56.0
	more than before	57	24.6
	much more than before	13	5.6
Ability to cope up with difficulties	much less than before	103	44.4
	same as before	103	44.4

	more than before	21	9.1
	much more than before	5	2.2
Enjoy normal day to day activities	much less than before	22	9.5
	same as before	144	62.1
	more than before	56	24.1
	much more than before	10	4.3
Face up your problems	much less than before	28	12.1
	same as before	117	50.4
	more than before	80	34.5
	much more than before	7	3.0
Unhappy and depressed	much less than before	92	39.7
	same as before	120	51.7
	more than before	18	7.8
	much more than before	2	.9
Losing confidence in yourself	much less than before	123	53.0
	same as before	89	38.4
	more than before	16	6.9
	much more than before	4	1.7
Yourself as a worthless person	much less than before	138	59.5
	same as before	85	36.6
	more than before	9	3.9
	much more than before	0	0.0
Reasonably happy, all things considered	much less than before	10	4.3
	same as before	67	28.9
	more than before	91	39.2
	much more than before	64	27.6
Headaches	much less than before	10	4.3
	same as before	67	28.9
	more than before	91	39.2
	much more than before	64	27.6
Fatigueness and exhausted	much less than before	22	9.5

	same as before	144	62.1
	more than before	56	24.1
	much more than before	10	4.3
Persistent Tension	much less than before	10	4.3
	same as before	67	28.9
	more than before	91	39.2
	much more than before	64	27.6
Aches and Pains	much less than before	51	22.0
	same as before	114	49.1
	more than before	59	25.4
	much more than before	8	3.4
Loss of voluntary control	much less than before	138	59.5
	same as before	85	36.6
	more than before	9	3.9
	much more than before	0	0.0
Gastrointestinal problems	much less than before	26	11.2
	same as before	83	35.8
	more than before	95	40.9
	much more than before	28	12.1

Interpretation: So, with the above frequency table, it can interpret that the majority (72.4%) of the respondents show high level of psychoneurosis, 7.8 % show moderate level of psychoneurosis while 19.8 % shows low psychoneurosis.

Pearson Correlation coefficient was used to measure the strength of linear relationship between overall psychoneurosis and the factors pertaining to psychoneurosis in the questionnaire as the responses were collected on Likert scale. From the given table we can see that Psychoneurosis is negatively correlated with independent variables such as age of the respondents, marital status, working experience and presence of stress other than job. It implies that when these variables increase psychoneurosis decreases. Also, Psychoneurosis is positively correlated with the independent variable i.e.; presence of adolescent children/aged parents. It implies that psychoneurosis increases with presence of adolescent children/aged parents in the family.

Table -3 Correlation between psychoneurosis and other variables

		Status of psychoneurosis	Age of the respondent	Marital Status of the respondent	Working Experience	Presence of stress other than job	Presence of adolescent children
Status of psychoneurosis	Pearson Correlation	1	-.082	-.055	-.065	-.068	.086
Age of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	-.082	1	.699	.310	-.126	-.254
Gender of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	.089	-.267	-.251	-.130	-.154	.039
Marital Status of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	-.055	.699	1	.256	-.063	-.266
Designation of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	-.072	-.046	.112	-.254	.423	.042
Working experience	Pearson Correlation	-.065	.310	.256	1	-.251	-.224
Presence of stress other than job	Pearson Correlation	-.068	-.126	-.063	-.251	1	.124
Presence of adolescent children	Pearson Correlation	.086	-.254	-.266	-.224	.124	1

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) ** correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2- tailed).

Discussion and Conclusion

From the study, it is found that the age of the respondents, marital status is independent of psychoneurosis. Psychoneurosis are dependent on designation of the employees i.e., resident doctors, nursing, administration, paramedical staff and security designations impact the level of psychoneurosis. As most of the respondents have work experience between 8 months to one year, it is found that the Psychoneurosis is dependent on working experience of the respondents. So, we can interpret that lesser the experience of the employee it is more likely to for them to develop the psychoneurosis or other related factors. Psychoneurosis is also found to be dependent on presence of stress other than that related to job (owning a car, house, personal problems etc.). Majority of the respondents shows high psychoneurosis i.e.; 72.4% while 19.8 % shows low psychoneurosis and only 7.8 % shows moderate psychoneurosis. Psychoneurosis has been evaluated for both mental and physical symptoms. On mental symptoms, the employees feel that they have lost much sleep due to worry. When the employee is not able to complete the given work, it leads to stress/worry and ultimately lost sleep. Most of the employees feel that usually (constantly) they are under strains due to less leave allotment and

heavy work load. Most of the employees feel that they can't cope with their difficulties. On physical symptoms, 95.7%, 90.5%, 95.7%, 88.8% and 77.9% of the respondents responded that they feel headache while doing work, fatigued and exhausted, feels tension, suffer from gastrointestinal problems and suffer from different aches and pains while working respectively. From the analysis the inference drawn is that respondents who are having high psychoneurosis are dissatisfied with their job; there is a negative correlation which indicates that if psychoneurosis increases job satisfaction decreases and the degree of correlation is less.

Psychoneurosis decreases with increase in age of the respondents, marital status, working experience and presence of stress other than job. Also, Psychoneurosis increases with presence of adolescent children/aged parents in the family.

To overcome these, the employees should be allowed to take frequent breaks to avoid boredom, regular exercise like aerobics, calisthenics martial arts, weight training, walking, jogging, cycling, swimming or etc. should be done. Even sports like football, badminton, tennis, table tennis and squash can be healthy exercise. Different stretches like neck stretches, back stretches etc. should be taught to relax the body during working hours. Learn to say 'no'. Slow down and be honest about what you can comfortably do. Meditation should be encouraged to achieve relaxation by clearing the mind of stressful outside interferences. Meditation is becoming more widely accepted in the U.S. as a relaxation technique. Meditation reduces heart rate, blood pressure, adrenaline levels, and skin temperature. Hospital staff should be provided with recreation facilities inside the hospital, to relax during their working hours so. As nurses, front desk executives and paramedical staffs were the major ones having high psychoneurosis, they should be rotated in duties so that the change in workload can provide them with a chance to spend time for them and to keep them motivated at work

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